

Border Trade and Vulnerability Context of Border Towns in Mizoram

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Abstract

Opening of borders for bilateral trade as a part of India's external policy has opened up an opportunity for bordering regions to integrate with larger economies. It marked the penetration of markets even in remote corner of borderlands which are normally located far from main markets. This has brought about a change in the way border's livelihood is organised and carried out. Employing a mixed-method of participatory and qualitative approaches, the paper examines the vulnerability context of Zokhawthar and Melbuk, two designated border towns on the Indian side situated along Zokhawthar –Rih border trade point. In understanding the vulnerability context upon which people based their livelihoods it provides a deeper understanding of emerging issues and challenges. There is a commonality in the forms of household experience vulnerability which are in a way intrinsically woven around border trade. Household livelihood vulnerability is centred around climatic induce vulnerability impacting employment, availability of food, and price volatility. At community and household level exposure to other forms of vulnerability ranges from structural to cultural in the form of change in policy, the spread of disease, and occupational health hazards.

Keywords: Border Trade, Household Livelihood, Vulnerability, Mizoram.

Introduction

Vulnerability connotes different meaning in its application depending upon the context of the study. The application of vulnerability concept ranges from health to developmental studies. It has found its application in the study of livelihood, poverty, and migration (Moret, 2014). Vulnerability can be understood in two ways. According to Chambers (1989), there are two sides of vulnerability: an external side of risks, shocks, and stress to which an individual is subjected, and an internal side which is defenceless, meaning lack of means to cope with damage or loss. According to Sustainable Livelihood Framework (SLF), vulnerability context is characterised as the existence of insecurities in the form of

- 1) Shocks
- 2) Trends, and
- 3) Seasonality

Shocks include drought, floods, disease, illness, and conflicts. Trends encompassed demographic, economic, technology trend, change in policy and environment. On the other hand, seasonality depicts a change in seasons and its impact on price and employment (Serrat, 2017). A livelihood is deemed to be sustained if it can cope and recover from stress and shocks and that people have adopted various mechanisms to mitigate those risks by adopting different coping strategies.

Robert Chambers (1995, 1989) work on poverty, vulnerability and livelihood which is based on participatory research methods introduced the

concept of vulnerability that relates to experiencing risk of various kinds at different levels of household, community, and national level. In studying livelihood in particular Levine (2014) argues for linking vulnerability to the study area. The basic premise is understanding how people assign their vulnerability rather than pre-assigning it. What may be deemed as part of vulnerability may not necessarily be assigned importance by the people. And this understanding is crucial in providing clarity on the interface between vulnerabilities and livelihood within the onus and perspective from people itself.

Examining into the vulnerability context and livelihood implications provide the nexus between the internal and external side of risks and the interface at household and community level. And this paper examines the vulnerability context of border towns whose livelihoods are greatly shaped by border trade. As livelihood is centred around people's experience and risks they associated with, any intervention drawn at a level beyond understanding their perception on vulnerabilities and challenges would prove to be unrealistic and irrelevant.

Zokhawthar –Rih Border Trade: A Tale of Two Border Towns

The second Indo-Myanmar border trade point was opened at Zokhawthar-Rih along the borders of Mizoram and the Chin State of Myanmar in 2004. Border trade commenced the following

year and was carried out under three mechanisms. One is the Traditional/Free Exchange Mechanism where it gives precedence to surrounding bordering villages for the exchange of 22 notified items across the borders as per the prevailing customary practice. The second is Barter Trade, where trade is allowed to carry out on 62 items including 22 items permissible under traditional mechanism of trade. Under these two mechanisms of trade, imported goods are balanced with an equivalent worth of exported goods and vice versa instead of monetary transaction as it is not permitted. The third mechanism corresponds to Normal/ Regular Trade where import and export is permitted under EXIM policy in freely convertible currency (Zokhawthar LCS report, 2018).

Prior to the formalisation of border trade, cross border trade as well as cross border movement was prevalent (Sangkima, 2004). However, as the region is tucked away from main markets and located deep in the extreme border, narratives of development along the bordering villages remain unaffected. As periphery regions have a greater tendency to be excluded from main developmental interventions, this region too does not receive much priority in the policy radar of development. But, this changes with the formalisation of border trade. Bordering regions located en route border trade zone began to receive attention and find their way in the narratives of development. Improving connectivity and injecting critical infrastructures became a priority along the trade zone. Planning was undertaken to facilitate the smooth functioning of formal trade. Construction works were carried out in different directions. Construction of two lane road connecting Champhai to Zokhawthar has been initiated. Construction of Land Customs Station (LCS) was completed in 2015 capable of hosting various offices of importance. Staff quarters, helipad was constructed at Melbuk (Khawnuam) village located 8 km from Zokhawthar. To facilitate border trade and regional development two adjacent bordering villages viz. Zokhawthar and Melbuk were elevated into border towns (Revenue town). Within a period of years, connectivity has improved and begun to transform bordering villages into a hub of economic activity. Besides, it churns the demographic scenario, out-migration is replaced by in-migration of people not only from intra- inter-district and interstate, but also received a host of international migrants compose mainly of ethnic Chin tribe of Chin Hills State and Sagaing Division of Myanmar.

Methodology

Vulnerability context of border towns is assessed in two stages using mixed methods of

participatory and qualitative approaches. In the first stage, seasonal mapping, a participatory technique, was drawn with the help of locals and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) was conducted with selected community leaders which comprise of representative member from the village council, voluntary organisations, teachers and trade-related groups. To understand the interface between vulnerability and challenges, focus group discussion was initiated along with community leaders of Zokhawthar and Melbuk. Effects of ascribed vulnerability at the household level and community level was drawn to depict interface of innate form of risks that are associated at a microscopic level which could in a way deprive people of their means of livelihood in the event it combines with larger external risks or stress.

Vulnerability Context of Border Towns

Pertinent to the study of livelihood entails understanding the vulnerability context of the household upon which it influences the outcomes of their livelihood. As Levine (2014) observed, vulnerability context is context-specific to the place of study and tends to be subjective in nature. What may be deemed as an issue may not necessarily be an issue in different stance and context. It is the amplification and manifestation that exudes in their lives that people assign to what constitute factors that form a part of their livelihood vulnerability. The basic assumption is people know best what entails in their experience of being in vulnerable situations. Following is the summary of findings.

Monsoon, Employment and Availability of Food

It is seen that across the two border towns, there is a commonality in terms of experiencing the phenomenon more or the less. There exists an intermittent linkage across the availability of food, employment, price volatility with the onset of monsoon. Monsoon season begins from May and lasted till September. Rainy season is the longest season in Mizoram. The state experience on an average of 257 cm of annual rainfall and monsoon season is spread across six months. The state experiences heavy downpour during the months of June, July, August till early September (Statistical Handbook Mizoram, 2018). About 40 % of rainfall is received during these months. During monsoon season, on account of incessant rainfall and considering the region's topography and nature of the terrain, landslide is a common phenomenon. Rockfall and debris landslides are common occurrences which destroy property, block roads halting supplies and factor in for price volatility of goods. The most affected are the people who depend on trade for their daily sustenance especially among porter. A porter in Zokhawthar shares his account during monsoon season,

There is fear among traders that their goods might get damaged and drivers of being stranded due to landslide or breakdown of vehicle. Normally, volumes of trade decrease during the rainy season. This greatly lessens our workload and reduces our earning capacity. On the other hand, prices of commodities increase partly to cover up the loss.

On account of monsoon, there is price volatility on goods. Roads from Champhai to Zokhawthar and from Rih across Chin Hills are in bad conditions. Landslide is a common phenomenon along the roads of trade. Despite the widening of Champhai-Zokhawthar road into 2 lanes, the topography and terrain of Mizoram which is made up of young, loose rocks pose a constant challenge during monsoon. At times, the occurrence of a landslide along the road level out developmental works, stranded vehicles and halted the supplies of goods. Traders cum suppliers, in turn, had to pay additional transportation cost and to recoup the extra cost, they had to increase the price of goods. As one trader who supplies goods to Aizawl stated,

During monsoon, we supply our goods slightly at a higher margin rate than on normal account to cover up additional cost we incurred. Sometimes our partner in Aizawl fails to understand when we do that. Considering the competitiveness and unstable nature of market there is always a fear of losing our business partner.

As local market orientation is based usually on trust, change in the price of a commodity could shake the very existence nature of the relationship at the same time business could deal loss on account of a competitive market. As market thrives on price competitiveness, small traders usually feel the burnt against big traders and big businessman. The accompany of monsoon season by a cyclone, windstorm and thunderstorm increase the degree of vulnerability. Mizoram has experienced a couple of cyclonic storms like Mora in 2017, Mahasen in 2013 and wind storms. Though it passes mildly unlike in other states causing havoc, the damage is felt in terms of losing property, crops and daily wage. It shuns carrying out economic activities. And considering in border towns where a majority of the population depend on daily wage employment working as porter, driver, it deprived people of their daily wages and reduced productive days.

For those villages near the border trade zone, dry season provides them with maximum employment opportunity. It is during this season, business thrived and accorded a higher number of passengers, tourists and visitors¹. However, on

another stride, there is water scarcity particularly during the month of January but it is not acute. For Zokhawthar, the existence of a perennial river Tiau acts as a source of water for domestic used during dry winter season.

Jhum cultivation is carried out mostly in Melbuk than in Zokhawthar. Few households in Zokhawthar own land for settle cultivation. The low lying flat basin along the river Tiau provide small space to carry out cultivation in Zokhawthar. As Zokhawthar village is curved out from Melbuk village, ownership of community land and forest for Jhum cultivation is low in the community. But the commonality across the border towns is that cultivation is carried out in a subsistence manner, mainly for household consumption. And people adhere to own small kitchen garden in their backyard which is less than sufficient. As Mizoram economy in itself is import oriented, bordering villages depend on the other side of the border for their consumption needs like vegetables, meat and other household needs.

Disease, Conflict and Policy.

Myanmar supply substantial requirement of meat to Mizoram as production capacity could not meet the high demand. Meat especially pork meat is consumed on a large scale, and it is imported on a large scale from Myanmar. Apart from pig, piglets are imported for rearing. In a rural household, people rear pigs as part of income security and form an important part of secondary income. In 2013, 2011, 2019 the Government of Mizoram has issued a ban to import pig and piglets mainly due to the spread of Porcine Respiratory and Reproductive Symptoms (PRRSV). The spread of bovine disease and blue ear pig disease affects not only the people residing along the border who had to depend on the other side of the border for their meat requirement but also local traders and pig farmers. On account of infectious disease, it impacts the availability of meat, business and rendered households who rear animals as secondary income to loss substantive amount of their investment. In the words of pig trader who formed the Piggery Association in Zotlang,

From the import of pigs and piglets, it supports more than 100 households and provides them with a steady source of income. With the onset of summer and warm weather, the spread of disease among animals is pronounced. In this situation, it affects us and some household who rear one or two pigs have to sell off before the disease caught hold at a lower price. And some forgo all their investment when their pigs/ piglets die.

Table 1 Seasonal Mapping of Zokhawthar and Melbuk.

Issues Months	Availability of Food	Availability of Employment	Availability of Water	Monsoon Season	Cyclone/ Windstorm/ Thunderstorm	Landslide	Cultivation Season
January	*** ###	*** ###	** ##				Clearing Jhum land
February	*** ###	*** ###	** ##				Burning
March	*** ###	*** ###	** ##				Burning
April	*** ###	*** ###	*** ###	* #	* #		Sowing of Kharif crops
May	*** ###	*** ###	*** ###	* #	* #		Sowing of Kharif Crops
June	** ##	** ##	*** ###	** ##	** * ###	** ##	Cleaning
July	** ##	** ##	*** ###	** * ###	*** ###	** ##	Harvest
August	** ##	** ##	*** ###	** * ###	** ##	*** ###	Harvest
September	*** ###	** ##	*** ###	** ##	* #		Sowing of Rabi crops
October	** * ###	*** ###	*** ###	* #	* #		Harvest
November	** * ###	*** ###	*** ###	* #			Harvest
December	** * ###	*** ###	*** ###				Harvest

Source: Field Survey

Scale of 3: Moderate/Frequent /Adequate= 3, Less/Low= 2, Very Less/ Low=1

Zokhawthar = *

Melbuk = #

Clearing forest/ Jhum land (December- January), Burning and Plantation (February - March), Sowing Seeds (April – May), Harvest (October – December)

With the formalisation of border trade, formalised groups with a different set of interest came into existence. Among the prominent groups, formed on account of trade can be clubbed into three broad categories viz., trader group, porter group and transport group. Under each group, diverse groups are formed within their self-interest. As each group wishes to have an upper hand in the way trade functions and manage, disputes often arise among different groups. At times some traders favour a particular porter body and transport body which intensify for future dispute. In another case conflict of interest arise among transport body and traders. During March 2019 dispute arose between Champhai Border Trade Transport Union (CTU) and Zokhawthar Village Transport body which escalated into violence and blocking of a trade

route. Earlier all freight services from Zokhawthar to Champhai on imported goods were under the control of CTU in which Zokhawthar transport body was also part of it. The contention was on the management of freight services as Zokhawthar decided to have more say in the way it was managed and started to collect additional fees for all vehicles passing through their village.

Table 2 Summary of Focus Group Discussion

Border Towns	Issues that impact at the Household level	Effects at Household Level	Issues that impact at Community level	Effects at Community Level
Zokhawthar	Occupational Hazards,	Health, Disability,	Dispute, Change in policy	Close down of Trade,

	Sickness	Death		Employment, Loss of Income
Melbuk	Occupational Hazards	Health, earning capacity is reduced	Spread of Disease Change in policy, Dispute.	Employment

Source: Field Survey

In response to it, CTU calls for roadblock and halted all vehicles near the entry point of Champhai. Even perishable goods were not allowed to pass and this has resulted in piling up of goods at Zero point, an important junction along the trade route. This sent panic across traders and merchants. Lorry drivers were the worst sufferers as they had to forgo their earning based on the number of consignments they ferry. During this dispute, the volume of trade registered was low. It reduced the earning capacity of porters as per day wage depend on workload and the kind of consignment that arrived. Earlier, vehicles carrying the consignment were allowed to enter till Zero point to load and unload goods where porters unload it and then load to another vehicle. However, the incident at Melbuk compels higher officials to undertake a stringent administration on FMR. The incident happened when some trucks of Melbuk carrying consignment were detained by Myanmar officials, some youth crossed the borders and stole away those trucks and drove back to India. When the matter was brought up to higher authorities, stringent law was implemented. As a result, porters now had to carry goods on head load from Zero point to the other side of the border, which is about 100 meters away.

Free Movement Regime (FMR) was in place along the Indo-Myanmar border to facilitate the movement of bordering population and trade. Although FMR has been limited to 16 km from the previous 40 km, in reality, people's movement beyond the permissible area is not curtailed. FMR may in itself not cause a health risk but may contribute towards vulnerability of the general population. With FMR in place, it assists for easy crossing over the border without hindrance and unmonitored (Chaudhury, 2019). In the absence of systematic cross border health surveillance border region are exposed to a greater risk of public health hazards. And along the Indo-Myanmar border non-security threat in the form of health hazards like HIV/AIDS, HIV-TB co-infection, HIV Hepatitis C (HCV), and vector-borne Malaria are pertinent with Myanmar remains the hub of illicit opium cultivation and drug trade centre

which makes it more alarming (ibid). Except for one NGO Mercy's clinic and one government run health sub-centre located at Zokhawthar and an Army dispensary at Rihkhawdar (Myanmar), across Indo- Myanmar border there are little efforts in building health care facilities.

Conclusion

The formalisation of border trade and opening of trade point along the borders of Mizoram and Myanmar brought along with it employment opportunities and for the region to draw its narratives of development. Connectivity has improved and it has promoted livelihood to household residing en route border trade zone. With it, it bridges village to village and those located at peripheral areas to partake in the dynamics of a market-oriented economy. Besides, it promotes the growth of people's institutions that rested and is driven solely by border trade. The onus of border trade rests in providing employment opportunity whereby bordering towns thrive on trade and are depended on trade for their sustenance. Despite the potential it garners, considering the vulnerability context upon which people base their livelihood, it remains constraint both from external and internal risks. Climatic induce vulnerability remains the major source of their vulnerability. And that climatic induce vulnerability affects employment, price of commodity and influences to some extent volumes of trade. Structural vulnerability in the form of policy, lack of infrastructure, and cultural vulnerability in the form of disputes and mobility contributed towards their vulnerability as well. Although border trade brought about a positive impact in the lives of those residing in border towns and creates its own space in the narratives of development, household's livelihood remains insecure in the face of conflict, change in policy and at the hands of climatic induce vulnerability. Occupational health hazards and dwindling health conditions on account of the nature of workload continued to form the biggest challenges at the household level. There is an urgent need to devise a strategy to lessen climatic induce vulnerability to build in greater resilience among the people. The internal side of risk which is apparent in occupational health hazards that affect their health needs proactive intervention in the form of securing social protection. This calls forth the need to strengthen health care services, upgrade and improvise facilities.

Note

¹Interview with a hotel owner and a caretaker of Tourist Lodge located at Zokhawthar.

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